

GROUP COUNSELING BASED ON MOSINTUWU VALUES TO REDUCE INTER-STUDENT CONFLICT

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Abstract

This research develops a group counseling service based on Mosintuwu values, a local wisdom of Poso community in Central Sulawesi, to reduce inter-student conflicts in multicultural schools. Mosintuwu values including togetherness, tolerance, peace-loving, and mutual cooperation were chosen as the intervention foundation because they have proven effective as conflict resolution mechanisms in post-conflict Poso. The research problem focuses on how to integrate Mosintuwu values into a contextual and relevant group counseling format for adolescent students. The research employs the ADDIE model to produce a group counseling module consisting of four structured sessions. This module integrates group dynamics with Mosintuwu values through interactive lectures, experience sharing, case analysis, role-playing, and peer support formation. The research results are expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of guidance and counseling based on Indonesian local culture, as well as practical benefits for school counselors and multicultural schools in creating a harmonious and tolerant learning environment.

Keywords: *group counseling, Mosintuwu values, inter-student conflict, local wisdom, cultural diversity*

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the countries that possesses extremely rich diversity or pluralism, in terms of ethnicity, race, culture, and religion. This diversity is reflected in more than 1,300 ethnic groups spread across the archipelago, each with its own unique language, traditions, customs, and belief systems. Indonesian culture is highly diverse because it is influenced by various historical and geographical factors, as well as interactions among different social groups (DZ Fuadah, 2024). Mosintuwu is a local cultural value originating from the Poso community in Central Sulawesi, particularly from the Pamona language. According to Mahfuddin et al. (2022), "Mosintuwu is a word in the Pamona language that means 'togetherness,' and Mosintuwu can be interpreted as togetherness, tolerance, love of peace, and mutual cooperation, which constitute the cultural roots of the Poso community in managing nature and social life." Based on the elements contained in Mosintuwu culture, there are character education values that can be meaningfully derived. The value of Mosintuwu, as the foundation of Poso local culture that emphasizes harmonious togetherness through the spirit of mutual support, can be holistically integrated into group counseling as a main aspect called mutual strengthening togetherness (integrative Mosintuwu). This includes operational indicators such as accepting differences in ethnic or religious backgrounds without prejudice while taking initiative to help friends in group tasks without expecting rewards, and participating in discussions that respect the opinions of others.

Adolescence is often associated with various myths and stereotypical views regarding deviant behavior and abnormality. This phenomenon is reflected in the numerous developmental theories that examine disharmony, emotional problems, and behavioral disorders that arise as a result of various pressures faced by adolescents, both those originating from internal transformations within themselves and those stemming from changes in their surrounding environment (Netrawati, 2018). Group counseling services are a form of assistance provided to individuals through group activities by utilizing group dynamics. This service enables each member to participate actively, share experiences with one another, and develop insights, attitudes, and skills. The purpose of group counseling services is to prevent the emergence of problems and to support the personal development of each member (Bakhrudin All Habsy et al., 2024).

According to Nadhifa et al. (2020), group counseling is one way to assist students in a preventive and cooperative atmosphere so that they feel comfortable and supported in their development. Group counseling aimed at improving student discipline is conducted using an approach that focuses on the realities of everyday life. Group counseling is designed to provide assistance to students who face difficulties and obstacles in interacting with their peers, including in completing developmental tasks. The presence of a group atmosphere that involves students who experience problems allows them to learn to be tolerant by mutually explaining the reasons behind their actions, which sometimes lead to conflict. This encourages the formation of affirmative attitudes among the participants (Syamila & Herdi, 2021).

The aspects of inter-student conflict that are holistically integrated in this study can be described as multidimensional interpersonal conflict, encompassing a cognitive dimension (perceptions and understanding) as the initial root where students process information, with indicators such as perceived threats or misunderstandings of peers' intentions (for example, interpreting a statement as an attack), inability to recognize cultural differences as triggers of conflict, and cognitive biases that lead to negative generalizations toward certain student groups, which are evaluated through questionnaire items exploring everyday thought patterns; and an affective dimension (emotions and feelings) that follows with emotional responses to tension, including the emergence of anger or frustration resulting from peer interactions, feelings of insecurity or anxiety in diverse groups, as well as the accumulation of negative emotions that affect learning motivation.

The main challenges faced in this study include the limited availability of empirical research that integrates local values such as Mosintuwu, resistance from students or teachers toward group counseling methods, and limited resources and facilitator capacity in implementing psychological interventions that are appropriate to the local cultural context. In addition, measuring outcomes such as "the reduction of inter-student conflict" requires valid and reliable instruments, which often becomes an obstacle in local research. The relevance of this topic in the fields of education and the counseling industry today is very high. Schools, as institutions for character building and learning environments, need to provide counseling services that are not only psychologically adaptive but also sensitive to local cultural values.

METHOD

This development research uses the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) to produce a group counseling module based on Mosintuwu values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The development resulted in a group counseling service module entitled "Group Counseling Service Module Based on the Local Wisdom Values of Mosintuwu to Reduce Inter-Student Conflict," which consists of four main sessions with a systematic structure of the Service Implementation Plan (Rencana Pelaksanaan Layanan/RPL). This module is specifically designed to be used offline by Guidance and Counseling (BK) teachers at SMAN 2 Pamona Selatan or other schools in the Poso region that have high cultural diversity.

The structure of the module consists of:

- a. Introduction (foreword, module objectives, table of contents, basic concepts of group counseling, Mosintuwu values, and the fundamentals of inter-student conflict).
- b. General guidelines for using the module.
- c. Core material comprising four sessions with the following details:

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Session	Title	Main Objective	Planned Core Activities
I	Introduction to Mosintuwu Values and the Basics of Conflict	To introduce Mosintuwu values as local wisdom and the factors causing inter-student conflict	Ice breaking, interactive lecture on Mosintuwu, sharing opinions about conflicts that have been experienced, small group discussions
II	Analysis of Mosintuwu Values in a Cultural Context	To understand the role of Mosintuwu values (tolerance, mutual cooperation, peace) in preventing conflict	Sharing cultural experiences, analysis of conflict cases due to lack of tolerance, personal reflection worksheets
III	Integration of Mosintuwu Values to Reduce Conflict	Melatih siswa mengintegrasikan nilai Mosintuwu dalam penyelesaian konflik secara konkret	To train students to integrate Mosintuwu values in concrete conflict resolution
IV	Group Support and Evaluation	To position students as agents of peer support and to evaluate the group counseling process	Training to become peer supporters, drafting a peer support contract, evaluation of the process and outcomes through reflection worksheets

Each session is equipped with service objectives, core materials, methods (interactive lectures, group discussions, role-playing, brainstorming, and reflection), media/teaching aids (Poso culture-themed PowerPoint presentations and student worksheets), activity procedures, as well as instruments for evaluating both the process and outcomes.

Quantitative Data Results

The assessment instrument used a 5-point Likert scale: Very Inappropriate (STS = 1), Inappropriate (TL = 2), Neutral (N = 3), Appropriate (L = 4), and Very Appropriate (SL = 5). The instrument consisted of two aspects:

- Aspect 1: Material Feasibility (10 items), covering the suitability of the Mosintuwu concept, integration of local values, conflict factors, module objectives, materials for Sessions I–IV, reference support, and relevance to the students' context.
- Aspect 2: Presentation Feasibility (10 items), covering module structure, language, session flow, supporting media, illustrations, visual design, adaptability, and feasibility of implementation in schools.

Content validity was calculated using Aiken's V formula.

1. Material Feasibility

Each item was evaluated using a Likert scale (1–5), and content validity was calculated using Aiken's V. The average Aiken's V value of 0.938 indicates that the material aspect as a whole is categorized as very feasible ($V > 0.80$). This shows that the module content is relevant, accurate, and effective in integrating Mosintuwu values to reduce inter-student conflict. The items with the highest V value (1.000) were item 3 (factors causing conflict), item 8 (materials for Session IV), and item 9 (reference support), indicating full agreement among the raters that these elements are strong and evidence-based.

Meanwhile, the items with the lowest V value (0.875) were items 1, 2, and 7, which are still considered feasible but may require minor adjustments, such as adding more contextual examples to enhance their alignment with student conflicts and the integration of local values. Overall, these results demonstrate that the module materials have been well designed to support educational objectives within the cultural context of Poso.

2. Presentation Feasibility

The results of the assessment by four expert validators on the 10 items of presentation feasibility, including structure, language, and visual design, yielded an average Aiken's V value of 0.906. This indicates that the presentation aspect is also categorized as very feasible ($V > 0.80$), showing that the module is easy to use, engaging, and suitable for implementation by school guidance and counseling teachers.

The items with the highest V value (1.000) were item 2 (language is easy to understand), item 4 (logical session flow), and item 8 (attractive visual design), reflecting strong agreement that these elements are effective for adolescent audiences and facilitators.

The items with the lowest V value (0.813) were item 3 (alignment of content with objectives) and item 5 (supporting media). Although still within the feasible category, these results suggest the need for improvements, such as adding more illustrations of local culture or refining the media to increase student engagement. Overall, the findings confirm that the module presentation effectively supports the offline counseling process, although minor revisions could further enhance its adaptability.

Qualitative Data Results

The qualitative data were obtained from feedback and revision suggestions provided by four expert validators through the module evaluation instrument. This feedback was collected through open-ended suggestion sections in the instrument, which included handwritten comments regarding the strengths, weaknesses, and recommendations for improvement of the module.

Expert	Comments and Suggestions
A1	<p>Written Suggestions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The group counseling module with positive values needs to clearly explain the views of amicus curiae in the process of constructing counseling findings to reduce conflict 2. From the perspective of the procedures undertaken in each step, a narrative and visualization should be developed before presenting the RPL.
A2	<p>Written Suggestions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The RPL should be complemented with follow-up actions. 2. The step-by-step procedures in the RPL must be described clearly and in detail. 3. It is recommended that meetings III/VI be conducted using role-playing techniques. 4. Add case examples to be discussed. 5. Attach the PPT to be used in each meeting.
A3	<p>Written Suggestions:</p> <p>Attach the PPT that will be used by the school counselor (BK teacher) in meetings 1 and 2 according to the material.</p>
A4	<p>Written Suggestions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The RPL should be adjusted to each meeting step. 2. Attach the PPT that will be used in each meeting.

No	Revision Results	Expert	Remarks
1.	The group counseling module with positive values requires clarification of ethical views and amicus curiae perspectives in the process of constructing counseling findings to reduce conflict.	A1	Revised
2.	Based on the procedures undertaken (e.g., what steps are followed?), a narrative and visualization should be developed before being incorporated into the RPL.	A1,A2, and A4	Revised
3.	The RPL has been complemented with follow-up actions.	A2	Revised
4.	It is recommended that Meetings III/VI be conducted using role-playing techniques.	A2	Revised
5.	Case examples available in Poso have been added.	A2	Revised
6.	The PPT to be used by the school counselor (BK teacher) in Meetings 1 and 2 has been attached according to the material.	A2,A3 and A4	Revised

Expert 1 requested a more detailed explanation of the appearance and mechanism of the group consultation feature via WhatsApp. Three experts (A1, A2, and A4) emphasized the need to strengthen research ethics aspects, particularly informed consent and data visualization. Expert 2 highlighted the importance of using more advanced programming techniques, adding role-playing activities in the third and/or fifth sessions, and incorporating real case examples from the guidance and counseling (BK) service post. In addition, three experts (A2, A3, and A4) requested that PowerPoint (PPT) materials for Sessions 1 and 2 be attached for use by BK teachers.

Discussion

The development of this module is grounded in the contextual needs of students in the Poso region, which still carries the collective memory of the horizontal conflicts of 1998–2001 and is characterized by high ethnic and religious diversity. The value of Mosintuwu, which means “selfless togetherness in both joy and sorrow,” was chosen as the main foundation because it has been proven to function as a conflict resolution mechanism within the local community (Mahpudz, 2023; Mahfuddin et al., 2022). The integration of this local wisdom value makes group counseling services no longer feel “foreign” to students, but instead relevant and closely connected to their cultural identity. The module was developed based on the principles of guidance and counseling instructional material development, namely being systematic, contextual, and learner-centered. The four sessions were sequentially designed, starting from the stages of awareness, analysis, practical application, and finally the internalization of values through peer support. This approach is in line with the stages of group counseling recommended by experts (Ed., 2016) and also takes into account the characteristics of adolescents, who are more responsive to experiential learning and group dynamics.

The strengths of the developed module include:

1. High cultural relevance, using Mosintuwu values as a “bridge” between counseling theory and the realities of students’ daily lives.
2. Practical and flexible, as each session can be adjusted in duration and depth of material by the guidance and counseling teacher according to the number of group members and the severity level of conflicts.
3. Encouraging active student participation, through role-playing and simulations, so that students are not only recipients of counseling services but also become agents of change within their school environment.
4. Comprehensive evaluation instruments, which facilitate guidance and counseling teachers in monitoring both the process and outcomes of the service without requiring complex external measurement tools.

This module addresses the gap in group counseling instructional materials that have so far been dominated by Western approaches and have not sufficiently accommodated local wisdom, particularly in post-conflict areas such as Poso. Therefore, this module is expected to serve as an alternative model of group counseling services that is contextual, easy to adopt, and effective in building social harmony in multicultural schools in Indonesia.

CONCLUSION

This development research successfully produced a Group Counseling Service Module Based on Mosintuwu Values that is valid and highly feasible for use (Aiken’s $V > 0.90$ for both content and presentation aspects). The module, which consists of four structured sessions, integrates the local wisdom values of Mosintuwu (togetherness, tolerance, love of peace, and mutual cooperation) as the main foundation of the intervention, making it more contextual and easily accepted by students in the Poso region and other multicultural post-conflict areas. All revision suggestions from the experts have been accommodated, including the addition of role-playing activities, real case examples from Poso, and attached PowerPoint materials, so that the final product is ready to be implemented by guidance and counseling teachers without requiring major modifications.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Guidance and Counseling (BK) teachers in the Poso region and other areas with high diversity are encouraged to immediately adopt and implement this module as a routine service for the prevention of inter-student conflict.
2. Large-scale field trials using a quasi-experimental design should be conducted to statistically measure the effectiveness of the module in reducing the intensity and frequency of conflicts.
3. A digital version of the module (in the form of an application or an interactive e-module) should be developed to make it more attractive to students and to facilitate documentation of the counseling process.
4. The module should be proposed to the Poso Regency Education Office and the Central Sulawesi Provincial Education Office to be used as standard teaching material for the training of BK teachers and to be distributed to all senior high schools and vocational schools in post-conflict areas.

5. Further research should be conducted by integrating other local wisdom values from different regions in Indonesia, so as to create a bank of culture-based group counseling modules representing the diversity of the archipelago.

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